

Table S4: Loadings obtained from the Principal Component Analysis on the 19 morphometric variables obtained from the *Teretrurus* samples after size correction using Thorpe's allometric formula. Bold values indicate strong loading with correlation > 0.3.

Character	Description	PC1	PC2	PC3
Standard deviation		3.523	1.642	1.033
Proportion of Variance		0.653	0.141	0.056
Cumulative Proportion		0.653	0.795	0.851
Eigen values		12.417	2.696	1.067
HL	Head length	-0.273	0.007	-0.071
HW	Head width	-0.258	0.007	-0.063
RL	Rostral length	-0.187	-0.168	-0.317
ED	Eye diameter	-0.244	-0.205	-0.071
OL	Ocular length	-0.272	-0.061	-0.037
IOD	Inter-orbital distance	-0.266	0.089	0.019
IND	Inter-nares distance	-0.250	-0.109	-0.217
SL	Snout length	-0.269	0.087	-0.016
FL	Frontal length	-0.257	0.143	-0.087
FW	Frontal width	-0.227	0.256	0.213
PL	Parietal length	-0.261	0.025	0.104
PW	Parietal width	-0.242	0.075	0.231
IPS	Inter-parietal suture	-0.182	-0.356	0.041
PFL	Prefrontal length	-0.116	0.531	-0.001
PFW	Prefrontal width	-0.248	0.002	0.027
IPFS	Inter-prefrontal suture length	-0.143	0.488	0.084
NL	Nasal length	-0.223	-0.319	0.044
NW	Nasal width	-0.240	-0.109	-0.107
INS	Inter-nasal suture length	-0.069	-0.214	0.834